

A study of the reading habits of the 21st century learners

Rachel Anne S. Agraviador*, Rhadelyn T. Briones, Patricia Anne A. Del Rosario,
Pauline Mariz M. Elloran, Maria Eloisa M. Joson
School of Arts, Sciences, and Education, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines

Abstract

Today, reading is no longer confined to printed materials since most 21st century learners prefer digital resources rather than the original printed resources. The researchers sought to uncover the reading habits of contemporary learners and share inputs based on the results of the study. The results of the study revealed that 21st century learners prefer digital reading material over printed reading material. This was due to the abundance of online resources available in the internet, which most of the 21st century learners prefer to read through digital formats. This indicates the transition to digital reading is based on the data gathered by the researchers. Findings also showed that 21st century learners read from online platforms like social media, text messages and websites on a daily basis. Readers tend to choose activities that they perceive at a lower cost. Respondents chose digital reading formats that are more convenient at a lower cost value on complex learning and retention of the information. Future efforts could focus on developing a reading module that will cater according to 21st century learners' reading habits. Future studies are also encouraged to make a wider scope of study.

Keywords: 21st century learners; Digital literacy; Reading habits; Contemporary period.

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Introduction

Reading is one of the most important language skills people have to acquire, learn, and master. It is a complex process that involves perception, comprehension, integration, and application. Through tests, observations, and a range of teaching techniques, several researchers have tried to explain how this occurs; one of the most well-known is the French psychologist Jean Piaget. According to Piaget (1936), acquiring sensory and motor data is the first step in learning to read and speak. As a result, reading experts believe that reading is a foundational ability that affects all aspects of a kid's scholastic achievement and is a crucial element for quality of life. This occurs between the time a child is born and when he or she is around two years old. Even physicians now understand the importance of parents reading to their young children. Reading books on boards and having books read frequently will help the baby understand the value of reading. Reading instruction begins at birth and lasts the duration of an individual's schooling (DiFino, 2017; Goldenberg, 2020). Students who continuously read have a higher chance of being motivated and improving their reading skills, while those who cannot read well tend to become discouraged and frustrated, which may lead to low proficiency in reading.

Nowadays, reading is no longer confined to reading print books. With the availability of reading materials that can be found on the internet, it has become easy and accessible to almost everyone. Indeed, the electronic version of printed materials allows the inclusion of other elements such as sounds and video clips, which cannot be found on regular printed material. One of the benefits that has led to the increasing purchase of e-books and e-journals in different libraries throughout the world is the flexibility in relation to time and space. Imagine having access to different, extinct, and hard-to-find printed materials with the help of digitally printed materials.

The ability to read is a gift of lifelong learning that has the capability to transform life and society. Students who have good reading habits will have excellent learning skills, knowledge, access to a wide range of information resources, and an effective retention capacity. Reading habits are essential tools for knowledge or information transfer. Therefore, it is vital to cultivate effective reading habits that will improve literacy. Libraries nowadays are encouraging the use and availability of digital resources. One of the rising concerns that educators need to take into consideration is the change in reading habits of 21st-century learners brought about by the rapid growth of technology.

Accordingly, the idea of "digital literacy" is one of many new literacies that have converged as a result of the impact of modern communication technologies. Digital literacy is characterized by the relationship between literacy and information technology. People are now living in an era of fast-changing technological changes. Reading online screens tends to be completely different from reading printed text. A lot of studies have shown that 21st century learners prefer internet resources to original printed material that is proven to have a negative impact on their reading habits. Some students use the excuse of "researching" on the internet primarily to use social media and chat with their peers and friends. Such activities are not related to academic purposes.

The main purpose of this study is to discover the reading habit preferences of 21st century learners and what they tell us about the literacy condition in the contemporary period. As future teachers, the researchers conducted this study to continuously adapt to the fast-paced fields of learning in order to teach effectively. In order to be effective and be able to cater to the needs of the students, the researchers must first understand the students' characteristics and preferences in reading. To do this, the researchers will identify the reading habits of 21st-century learners to redirect effective learning by looking into their preferences in reading.

Theoretical Framework

According to Nilsen et al. (2012), a habit is a behavior that is repeated until it loses its automaticity, is carried out without thinking about it, and is mostly unaware of it. As stated by Gardner (2012), habit is a concept without a single authoritative definition. People repeated actions out of habit without thinking about why this self-concept was essential. According to psychologists, habits are routines of behavior that are frequently repeated and frequently happen unconsciously. Reading habits can significantly aid pupils in achieving academic success as a subliminal self-concept. They have to perform these habits to develop them as reading habits. Thus, it can be claimed that habit involves an unconscious patterning process as it pertains to recurring acts. It exhibits a person's personality, whether positive or negative, and they go frequently. Reading regularly will aid the learner in acquiring knowledge that matters and in achieving success in the classroom.

Figure 1. Subjective-Task Value Theory

The value that students place on particular activities or subjects, according to Oschatz (2015), is one of the aspects recognized to be important for students' learning decisions within educational motivation research. Based on the expectancy-value hypothesis (Eccles & Wigfield, 2002), students' achievement behavior is thought to be influenced by their subjective task value and their competence beliefs. Four elements of job value were discovered by Eccles and Wigfield (2002). The personal relevance of performing satisfactorily on a task connected to the potential for validating key elements of an individual's self-schema is first described as the achievement value. Second, the delight a person derives from participating in an activity that links that value to perceived interest is referred to as intrinsic value. Third, utility value is defined as the contribution a work makes to the accomplishment of future objectives. Last but not least, the perceived cost includes all the drawbacks of performing a task. The model presupposes that task-specific beliefs have some influence on achievement values. The task value in reading is the level of the task's difficulty that influences whether someone is likely to perform it repeatedly, increasing or reducing it.

Literature Review

Reading Habit

Most research has been conducted to define reading habits. According to Davidovitch et al. (2016), a reading habit is organizing an individual's reading. Researchers further stated that developing good reading habits involves recalling letters, words, phrases, paragraphs, and entire texts. Reading should be encouraged. Reading habits should be encouraged by parents and teachers. In another study, Mercado et al. (2015) said that reading is extremely needed for learning. Reading attitudes show students the reasons why they read. With the assistance of reading attitudes, the reading habits of the students are specified. Awoyemi and Yusuf (2016) added that most library users possess reading habits; however, some of them even manage to pass their examinations. But most people read to increase their knowledge.

Reading Format

Cognitive research from the past decade suggests that readers' deep learning mechanisms, memory, and focus depend on the text's presentation mode, whether it be print or electronic. There are several studies that aim to investigate the reading format preferences of readers. The Digital Textbook Collaborative (2012) stated that digital textbooks are rapidly replacing traditional textbooks in classrooms. It is uncontrollable and will continue to move quickly into the near future (Roskos & Neuman, 2014).

According to Walker (2017), digital reading is part of the lives and learning of 21st-century learners. The author said that if learners are asked today to choose a reading format that they want, digital always wins. Walker (2017) explained that students read faster in digital formats because they process information faster than reading printed materials.

On the contrary, O'Malley (2017) mentioned that most students chose printed books over novels and textbooks in their teacher's class. There are students who prefer to use printed copies for reading. According to Mizrachi et al. (2018), Zipf's concept of the Principle of Least Effort may aid in explaining how and why readers express varying preferences for different format types in relation to various reading tasks and material categories. The theory states that an actor will choose the course of least effort or of least resistance to obtain results that are at least acceptable. This theory suggests that readers would weigh the simplicity, cost, and convenience of digital reading with the amount of time and effort needed to extract sufficient knowledge from the content for the task at hand when choosing a reading format. A reader may well prefer an affordable, lightweight electronic version if all that is required of the text is a delightful experience since it does the job done and the worth placed by the reader on complicated learning and retention of the material is minimal.

According to Ackerman and Goldsmith (2011) and Foasberg (2014), long academic books and long-form reading in print are preferred by students (as cited by Aharony & Bar-Ilan, 2016). Another researcher, Barshay (2019), mentioned that even the teacher encouraged their students to use digital format for reading to save money or to look for available free resources online, but the students said that they prefer to read in paper format.

Reading Material Preference

Various studies that state the importance of reading material preferences were conducted. Can et al. (2010) highlighted that in order for reading to be productive and for the reader to establish a purpose, readers should define themselves with what they choose. The significance of readers' reading preferences was highlighted by this study (as cited by Aydin & Ayranci, 2018). According to Batur et al. (2010), reading instruction should take students' degrees of interest into consideration (as cited by Gezgin et al., 2021). Barnes (2019) said that students choose their reading material because it captures their attention and motivates them to read. According to Lee (2019), if students are allowed to choose what they want to read, it will help them to learn more and seek out more information about their chosen reading material.

Wolpert-Gawron (2018) added that if people have freely chosen what they want to read, it means new ideas from them are accepted and allowed to show what titles or genres they like best. Furthermore, Akarsu and Dariyemez (2014) stated that the transition from reading on paper to reading online is influenced by pupils' preferences and motivation (as cited by Tanjung et al., 2017).

Reading Frequency

More than half of the 9.9 million learners in the last school year of 2015–2016 read less than 15 minutes per day. The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) revealed that the link between reading engagement and performance was solid and significant in 32 countries, including the United States. Based on American students' PISA scores, reading engagement had a higher correlation with reading literacy achievement.

In the Philippines, the Statista Research Department (2018) published a statistical analysis that shows the frequency of book reading among Filipino adults in 2017. According to the findings, 17% of the respondents claimed to read a book every day. The majority of respondents—49.2 percent—said they read a book once a week.

Modern Reading

According to Brown (2016), students are able to interact with many people through the use of electronic text. The interactive elements of digital texts enabled students to stay focused on reading, lengthen reading sessions, and engage in peer discussions that improved comprehension. The acceptance of these new forms of literacy in the classroom can be highly inspiring and empowering for today's pupils because 21st century learners are highly skilled in technical discourses. When technology is implemented in the classroom in significant ways, digital text can be especially effective for English language learners who are having trouble learning.

Students in the 21st century need various kinds of literature access than were commonly used in the past. Due to the innovative world of new literacies in which students are now immersed, committed, and motivated for reading to be learned, one-choice independence book talk and modern literacies are incorporated into conventional independent reading activities. Changes can be made to improve student participation and motivation for reading. Classroom teachers associate classroom standards with the standard practices of non-school students. Kahraman (2017) added that online books will break our habit of reading text-based books. Likewise, Owusu-Acheaw and Larson (2014) said that if students volunteer to read, there is a positive effect on their academic performance. Davidovitch et al. (2016) added that students will read and get information on screen. This means that students use technology all the time rather than grabbing a book.

More than an hour is spent online each day by digital natives on both their respective computers and mobile phones. Only 50% of the people in this generation watch television for this amount of time every day. The majority of millennials spend at least one hour each day watching TV and using their computers, whereas just 60% of them use their smartphones for longer than an hour every day. The desktop is used by the majority of baby boomers for longer than an hour each day, followed by the television. Only 40% of those in Generation X are also using their phones during this time period. These facts must be understood in order to effectively communicate with a company's target market. According to Oza (2017), young people's reading preferences and literacy development are greatly influenced by technology. It is important that reading in print is not left behind, despite the beneficial impact that technology has on giving young people more reading possibilities. If computers have taken the place of traditional literacy, it is interesting that teachers, authors, publishers, and software developers may collaborate to produce more engaging and affordable online resources for students based on their reading preferences and habits.

According to YPulse (2020), the preferred reading material of post-millennials is digital books, like e-books, websites, and social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. They prefer to watch and listen rather than read because they lose their attention easily. However, printed books are still useful for this generation if they are needed. Issa et al. (2014) conducted a study on the effects of information and communication technologies (ICT) on the reading habits of students and found that they have access to a variety of technology, including smartphones, computers, iPads, and the Internet, and they utilize it more for entertainment than for learning.

Reading and Digital Literacy

According to Delgadova (2015), reading literacy is a broad range of reading knowledge, skills, and aptitudes required for successful textual interaction. Reading literacy therefore refers to the capacity to correctly understand the contents, identify both explicit and implicit significance, analyze the material and the data received, and be able to appropriately interpret the contents and transmit them. However, in the first place, it is the capacity to assess texts independently and use the knowledge gained to innovate and produce new learning. The use of technology gave way to the formation of a new form of literacy. Forms of thinking and skills that are not as easily enabled by conventional literacy are made possible by digital literacy.

Given that the current generation of students has only experienced technology from a consumer standpoint, Ventimiglia and Pullman (2016) noted that the requirement for pupils to master skills in digital literacy should not come as a surprise. The present generation of learners first encountered technology as a tool for amusement and social interaction, as opposed to earlier technologists who first encountered it in the profession before figuring out how to integrate it into their personal lives. Students must now learn how to use technology in both educational and work environments while being brought up with access to a growing amount of it.

Digital literacy, as defined by the American Library Association's task force on the topic, is the capacity to use information and communication technologies to locate, assess, produce, and convey information. It calls for both cognitive and technical abilities (Newton, 2019). Digital literacy abilities are thought to grow together with literacy skills, particularly as young children become increasingly at ease applying digital media as tools (Blanchard & Moore, 2010).

Statement of the Problem

The study aims to investigate the reading habits of 21st century learners. Specifically, it answers the following questions:

1. What are the reading habits of the 21st Century Learners in terms of:
 - a. Preference of Reading Format
 - b. Preference of Reading Material
 - c. Hours Spent in Reading
2. What do reading habits talk about the condition of the literacy of the 21st century learners in the contemporary period?

Significance of the Study

The findings of this study provide information that can be used as a reference to improve the reading habits of 21st-century learners. The result of the study will be useful in understanding the reading habits of 21st century learners in terms of reading format and reading material preference.

Teachers will determine the reading habits and preferences of 21st-century learners. With this information, the teacher can decide which reading format and materials can be used to improve learners' reading habits. Students will be able to identify their reading habits and reading preferences. This information will help them to self-assess, guide, and plan how they are going to develop their reading habits. Parents will have information about their child's reading habit. This will help them find possible intervention or enhancement opportunities for their children. School administrators can use the results as the basis for decision-making about the policies, facilities, and reading programs they will use in school. Future researchers can use this as the basis for their future studies.

Scope and Limitation

This study is primarily focused on discovering the reading habits of 21st century learners in terms of their preferences and hours spent reading. Respondents randomly selected Grades 4 to 9 students. The scope of the present study is limited geographically to the province of Cavite. The researchers gathered data from ten (10) respondents in each grade level. The number and variety of respondents were reduced to fewer numbers. As cited previously, it is due to the imposed community lockdown as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. The data was gathered and converted to online questionnaires instead of pencil and paper questionnaires.

Methodology

The researchers used a quantitative descriptive method to collect data for the study. Online questionnaires through a Google form were used for data collection. In this study, 60 respondents between the ages of 10 and 14 years old, from Grade 4 to Grade 9, participated in the province of Cavite. Researchers used random sampling to determine the number of respondents. Random sampling was used to decide

which students would take the reading habit questionnaire. A portion of the statistical population called a simple random sample is one in which each member has an equal chance of being chosen. A simple selection at random is intended to offer an objective depiction of a group (Hayes, 2019).

The researchers adopted a quantitative survey instrument developed by *Erasmus + Handbook for Reluctant, Struggling, and Poor Readers*. It is a project co-funded by Erasmus+ for the European Union Handbook for reluctant, struggling, and poor readers in 2016. The project offers an approach centered on the individual that is essential for successfully tackling reading problems and preventing growing gaps in secondary school.

The researchers consulted advisers, experts, and grammarians in making a reading habit questionnaire. The reading habit questionnaire was approved by a group of validators. When mobility became limited because the country was placed under quarantine, the researchers converted the reading habit questionnaire into an online questionnaire through a Google Form. The researchers looked for teachers and parents around Cavite who are related and have connections via online for respondents from Grades 4 to 9. After coordination was made with teachers, invitation messages together with an explanation of the purpose of the study were sent to the teachers and parents, as well as a link to the online questionnaire and consent form. Respondents were requested to answer each question as honestly as possible in order to obtain accurate results. The researchers informed the teacher, parents, or respondents if their submission was confirmed.

Quantitative approaches focused on exact measurements and statistical or numerical interpretation of data obtained via surveys, polls, and other types of questionnaires, as well as the manipulation of statistical data that has already been collected using frequencies and percentages (Bloomfield & Fisher, 2019).

Results and Discussion

Question 1: What are the reading habits of the 21st Century Learners in terms of reading format preference?

Figure 2. Respondents' reading format preferences

The figure shows that 35 out of 60 respondents (58.3%) prefer reading from digital formats, while the remaining 25 respondents (41.7%) prefer reading from printed materials. There are more respondents who prefer reading digital formats over printed materials.

Table 1 reveals the relationship between the grade levels' preferred reading formats. Grades 4, 5, and 7 respondents (N = 10) have an equal percentage of preferred reading materials. Fifty percent of Grades 4, 5, and 7 respondents preferred printed materials, while the other 50% preferred to read in digital formats. On the other hand, Grades 6, 8, and 9 respondents have a higher preference for digital formats (50%, 80%, and 60%, respectively) over printed formats, which comprise only 40%, 20%, and 40%, respectively. The table shows that most of the 21st century learners (Grades 6, 8, and 9 respondents) prefer digital reading

formats to printed reading formats. However, the remaining learners (Grades 4, 5, and 7) are neutral, having equal preferences for both printed and digital reading formats.

Table 1. Respondents' percentage of preferred reading format per grade level

Grade Level	Printed Format	Frequency	Digital Format	Frequency
Grade 4	50%	5	50%	5
Grade 5	50%	5	50%	5
Grade 6	40%	4	50%	6
Grade 7	50%	5	50%	5
Grade 8	20%	2	80%	9
Grade 9	40%	4	60%	5

Question 2: What are the reading habits of the 21st century learners in terms of reading material preference?

Table 2. Respondents' reading materials preferences

Reading Material	Mean	Priority
Academic Books	11.43	17
Storybooks	10.40	16
Websites	10.23	15
Sports Programs	9.18	14
Comics	9.05	13
Magazine	8.57	12
Manuals	8.48	11
Blog	8.42	10
Dictionary	8.40	9
Encyclopedia	8.23	8
Playscripts	8.10	7
Road Signs	8.03	6
Catalogs and Brochures	8.02	5
Recipes	7.97	4
Poetry	7.95	3
Atlas	6.90	2
Newspaper	6.47	1

The table shows that academic books were the most preferred, with a mean value of 11.43. Next are storybooks (10.40), followed by websites (10.23), sports programs (9.18), comics (9.05), magazines (8.57), manuals (8.48), blogs (8.42), dictionaries (8.4), encyclopedias (8.23), playscripts (8.1), road signs (8.03), catalogs and brochures (8.02), recipes (7.97), poetry (7.95), and atlases (6.9). The newspapers appeared as the least preferred reading material, with a mean value of 6.47.

Figure 2 shows the frequency with which the learners read the different reading materials. The color coding indicates if the material is being read once a month (orange), once a week (yellow), almost every day (green), or never or hardly ever (brown). The reading material that learners read almost every day is social media (75%), followed by text messages (58.3%), websites (46.7%), and storybooks (36.7%). The table supports the result of Table 1 that 21st century learners prefer to read on social media, text messages, and websites, which are part of digital reading materials.

Figure 2. Frequency in reading different reading materials

Figure 3. Frequency in terms of reasons for reading

Figure 3 shows that more respondents are reading for school requirements on a daily basis (50%), once a week (41.66%), and once a month (8.33%), and none of the participants answered they never read for school requirements. The figure also shows that respondents read for fun and relaxation on a daily basis (46.7%), followed by once a week (38.33%), once a month (13.33%), and never (1.66%). This result explains the data in Table 2, where the respondents chose academic books as their preferred reading material. According to this result, 21st-century learners are required to read books for academic purposes.

Question 3: What are the reading habits of the 21st Century Learners in terms of hours spent in reading?

The graph shows that out of 60 respondents, 22 (36.7%) declared that they only read an hour per week, 17 (28.3%) respondents spend two hours in reading per week, 9 (15%) spend three hours per week, 3 (5%) spend four hours per week, 3 (5%) spend five hours per week, 1 (1.7%) spend seven hours per week,

1 (1.7%) spend nine hours per week, 1 (1.7%) spend 14 hours per week, 1 (1.7%) spend 40 hours per week, and 2 (3.3%) spend 48 hours of reading every week.

Figure 4. Respondents’ number of hours per week spend in reading

Question 4: What do the reading habit talk about the condition of the literacy of the 21st century learners in the contemporary period?

Based on the results, 21st century learners are in the process of building their digital literacy. This is supported by our findings that a greater percentage of respondents preferred digital reading material (58.3%) over printed reading material (41.7%). The 16.6% difference in percentage between those who prefer digital reading and printed reading materials implies that while a larger percentage of respondents prefer reading digital content, quite a few still prefer reading books. This is in line with the results of the 2017 Readership Survey from the National Book Development Board (NBDB), which showed that most Filipinos still read books in print. This outcome suggests that offering print learning materials is still a preferred alternative.

In addition to this, researchers found out that respondents' preferred reading materials are also in digital format, such as social media, text messages, and websites. Based on the study of Dagadova (2015), in collecting information faster and more effectively, new technologies have created several advantages and opportunities. However, they restrict the growth of reading literacy. Having academic books as the most preferred reading material shows that 21st-century learners prioritize academic needs. The next preferred reading materials are storybooks, websites, and sports, which tell us that 21st century learners are reading for recreation. Based on the joint statement of the International Reading Association, Canadian Children’s Book Centre, and National Council of Teachers of English (2014), young people are considerably more likely to succeed as readers if they find reading enjoyable and read frequently outside of school.

The newspaper appeared to be the least preferred reading material. This is supported by the 2017 Readership Survey result that shows only 8.73% of the Filipinos read to keep up with current events. Analyzing the respondent’s result in terms of the number of hours spent reading, 65% indicated that they read one to two hours per week. The weekly average of hours spent reading is 4.6 hours. The result is less in comparison to the results of 2017 Readership Survey, commissioned by the National Book Development Board (NBDB) that has 35.54 (8.89 hours weekly) hours that the early stages used in reading printed and digital format. This specifies that the 21st century learners’ reading hours tend to drop in numbers.

Conclusion

The findings of this study revealed 21st-century learners' reading habits. 21st century learners generally prefer to read through digital formats rather than printed material. However, there is only a 16.6% difference between the digital reading format and the printed reading format preference. This indicates that the transition to digital reading is taking place, especially since the data was gathered during the quarantine period. This is supported by the findings that 21st century learners read from online platforms like social media, text messages, and websites on a daily basis. This result is in line with the theoretical understanding of the perceived cost. Readers tend to choose activities that they perceive to have a lower cost. This applies in reading when respondents choose digital reading formats that are more convenient, and the value placed by the reader on complex learning and retention of the information is low.

The findings of this study emphasized that 21st century learners most frequently read materials that are digitally published. As mentioned in the subjective task theory, the preferred reading materials have intrinsic value in forming the reading habit. Learners who read their preferred reading material get enjoyment from the activity and are more likely to do it repeatedly, which eventually develops into a habit. The results also emphasized the importance of attainment value and utility value in forming reading habits. This was reflected in the result that 21st-century learners prioritize reading academic books.

Additional findings said that a greater number of respondents who stated that they read books for academic requirements support this notion. In line with the subjective task theory, learners prioritize reading material that they perceive to have personal importance and purpose. The description of the result points out how 21st century learners adapt to the abundance and boom of technology and online resources. 21st century learners are the generation of learners that acquire digital literacy. They make use of these resources by reading various available reading materials. This new generation of learners takes advantage of this opportunity by using their skills to process large amounts of information.

It cannot be denied how rewarding reading is; aside from enhancing communication skills and academic purposes, it also helps reduce stress. If teachers want the students to read, they should encourage them by leading by example and talking about the book that they are reading with them. Many students do not like to read because it is hard for them. Teaching children reading strategies and laying out the benefits of reading is the best way to enhance their appreciation and encourage them to pick up a book of their own and read with confidence.

Recommendation

The researchers recommend the following: English teachers should be good motivators for the students. Teachers should encourage the students to read at home so that good reading habits can be developed and sustained. Students should make use of technology to develop good reading habits. The school should support and provide reading facilities that contain both digital and printed materials that can enhance and sustain the full potential of students in reading. Guidance and supervision by the teacher are a must in case the attention of the students using digital formats is diverted to unrelated stuff. What is important is that it will cater to the students' needs. Based on the results of the study, future efforts could focus on determining the non-reading activity that takes away students reading time. The respondents in this study were also limited to a small number of public students. Future studies can expand their scope by including more public school students as respondents.

This study only included students in grades 4 through 9. However, this study can be expanded by looking at all grade levels at the primary and secondary levels. Similar studies should be conducted in the future with a larger population to achieve a broader generalization. This is significant because, as the researchers adapt to the new normal in teaching and learning, they must discover and process the reading habits of the 21st century learners, who will be the future leaders of the country.

To help learners succeed, teachers should gradually cultivate an appreciation of reading and intrinsic drive. Students who want to read more frequently are nonetheless better readers than those who lack reading motivation. Teachers might start by adopting methods of instruction that have been proven to motivate children. Teachers must know what motivates kids at different ages. It has been demonstrated that engaging texts, more hands-on activities, providing students with clear objectives to strive towards, delivering rewards or incentives in specific circumstances, and enabling students to take part and work in groups all help to motivate students.

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